

MUTUAL INTEGRATION OF SCHOOL AND MUSEUM ACTIVITIES IN EDUCATING STUDENTS IN THE ROLE OF RESPECT FOR SPIRITUAL HERITAGE.

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Annotation: This article contains thoughts and opinions about museums, their types, their importance in students' respect for spiritual heritage, family values and the role of museums in child education.

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THE ROLE OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES IN CHILD EDUCATION. Raising a young generation in our country who is physically healthy, spiritually mature, harmonious and well-developed in all aspects, independent-thinking, has intellectual potential, deep knowledge and a modern outlook, and is able to take responsibility for the fate and future of our country. The family is primarily responsible for continuing the task of growing up. Looking at the birth of a mentally and spiritually healthy child as the result of the work of a healthy and harmonious family, it is the duty of each of us to create an environment of mutual respect and love, high moral and spiritual values in the family. National and universal values play a very important role in fulfilling this task. Values are the basis of the development of society, a powerful factor that transfers the successes achieved in the historical development of the nation from generation to generation. Looking at the stages of historical development, every society and state did not develop without developing and strengthening its national values. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired the video selector meeting held on January 19, 2021 on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard: "If society if the body of his life is economy, his soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values. So what is value? Values mean all the things that are important for a person and humanity. We interpret the essence of values by fully conveying, teaching, and educating the traditions of people's historical experience to future generations. Therefore, it is an urgent matter to respect, honor, sincerely fulfill national spiritual values and keep them in their original state, and at the same time, to harmonize universal human values in the family environment. Values are divided into different types and cover all aspects of life. In particular, a person and his life are the highest value. There is no need to talk about the value of something where there are no people. That is why honoring the dignity of a person, improving his life, developing his knowledge and cultural level, maintaining his health, and protecting his life are the main directions of our state's policy.

The role of museums in the system of educational work. Independent Uzbekistan has found a place among the most advanced countries in the world, has a worldview of

independence for its stable development, is filled with a sense of national pride, is free and free-thinking, and at the same time has a deep sense of civic responsibility. makes it his task to bring up a person who feels national and universal values to the extent required by his profession and social environment. We are happy and proud that in our independent Uzbekistan, great attention is being paid to the issue of educating young people in a comprehensive manner. It is not difficult to teach a young person to tie his neck well and behave well in the theater. It is difficult to understand that the heritage of the past generations is a vital need, it is not just a goal, but a necessary condition for the further development of culture. After all, life does not stand still. If today we like microcalculators, tomorrow computers will become a necessity. Those who do not understand this and hope to live with the scraps left by the almonds, will surely fall behind in life. National pride is a person's honoring of the village or city where he was born and grew up, where his umbilical blood dripped, the place of his ancestors, descendants and ancestors, honoring his parents, brothers, relatives, the past of his country. , is reflected in being proud of today and the future. That's why, in today's conditions of building a new society, as the President said: "The feeling of the motherland, the concept of the motherland should be as holy as a place of worship, pure and great as a place of worship..." National pride is about loving the Motherland. not lofty words, calls, slogans, but truly honest work for the bright future of the country, for the people, for the well-being of the nation. It is a sign of patriotism to love the motherland from the heart, to mobilize all knowledge, abilities, and strength for her benefit. The feeling of national pride is the complete opposite of national arrogance, national conceit, and national bragging. Cultural heritage plays an important role in the formation of national pride. Because cultural heritage is the value of every nation. Cultural heritage, which is the fruit of human intelligence, is a collection of material and spiritual values of the people that are passed from one generation to another. For this reason, in the enrichment of cultural heritage, it is very important to comprehensively assimilate national and universal values, to have a deep knowledge of the achievements of world culture and to follow them. Comprehensive study of our cultural heritage accelerates the formation of national pride in young men and women who are the future of our society. The monuments, which amaze the whole world and dazzle and amaze thousands of tourists, have united famous scientists, philosophers, poets, calligraphers, artists, raised the mood of the citizens and gave them spiritual strength during the rallies and marches. , and called the young people to be polite and moral, to be honest and clean, to be courageous, to be courageous and to protect the homeland. Conveying the truth about the cultural heritage of our people to young people will help to build national pride in them. Education of a fully developed, spiritually mature person, which is one of the most urgent problems of today, is being implemented in a unique way in all aspects of our society. In the conditions of today's self-awareness and the strengthening of our independence day by day, there is no more sacred duty for every child of the Motherland than to love, study and cherish the history of the Motherland. That is why the past is historical and material and cultural. great importance is attached to solving the problems of studying monuments, increasing the role of protection.

I. A. Karimov's booklet "There is no future without historical memory" contains a number of historical issues of deep scientific importance, which cannot be discussed about the future of our nation without having a clear idea of how to solve them. . After gaining independence, several new and important problems appeared before our people. Their essence and meaning

are primarily related to ensuring the all-round development and prosperity of our nation. I. A. Karimov in his article on the current problems of the science of history pointed out the important directions in this regard: "To restore spirituality, in order for a person to walk with his head held high and not feeling inferior to others in the country where he was born and raised, of course, historical memory is needed." In front of our nation, which is rich in history and has an ancient culture dating back to the distant past, to learn more about its past, origin, ancestors, traditions, spiritual wealth, high culture, art, the task is to understand and directly continue. As the President emphasized that "... history is the basis of national spirituality", every citizen of an independent country, especially the youth who determine its future, must know their history and culture well. Museums, among all cultural and educational institutions, make their due contribution to the formation of historical memory, its development, and at the same time, to the creation of feelings of national pride in the spirit of the current generation. While we get theoretical knowledge from textbooks and manuals, practical exhibitions and museums with material evidence directly serve to further strengthen this theoretical knowledge. At the same time, the philosophical heritage is also an integral and fundamental part of the people's spirituality. In fact, history, historical memory is one of the most important sources of formation and development of socio-philosophical heritage. Therefore, both of them are the object of understanding human activity, people's way of life, the general essence of the historical process. That's why the thoughts of our head of state, "Understanding one's identity begins with knowing history" and "It is impossible to understand one's identity without knowing the true history" are very valuable. It should be said that in understanding history, it is necessary to study it not only in relation to production factors, as in the recent past, but to understand it in all its aspects, especially as the main source and basis of our spirituality. Historical memory - every nation, nation's understanding of its place in time and space, its lineage, its identity, its real history, its place in terms of spirituality and culture, its contribution to its development, is an independent and objective realization of his national pride. Of course, if the nation has its historical memory and historical consciousness, it will inevitably understand and interpret the historical and social processes it has experienced more deeply. These attempts are embodied in the scientific activities of the people's representatives - scientists, thinkers, and are manifested by them in the scientific-theoretical analysis of society, human life and spirituality, and in the creation of its known theory and principles. The spiritual values, i.e. "paths", formed in the life of a person and society and later forming the basis of historical memory, are preserved and developed as a spiritual heritage through the inner world of the next generations. A certain spiritual factor unites people as a certain group, community. Spirituality is based on a long history and embodies the spirit of all past people, generations, that is, their thoughts, ideas and beliefs. The spiritual factor is very complex and multifaceted, and it certainly includes historical memory and national consciousness. Because they develop in connection with each other and lead to each other's improvement. Of course, the history and national consciousness of each people, which covers the historical memory of the nation, also reflects the belonging to a certain religion.

As the museums serve as a factor of revitalization of historical memory, the materials displayed in them are very valuable because they reflect the characteristics of their time as physical evidence, as well as the message they give about the culture and art of that time. They attract the attention of the audience with their features based on the highly developed culture,

literature, art and spiritual outlook of our people. The charm, magic, geometric precision, chemical perfection, and the precise and sophisticated designs of construction and architectural structures directly reflected in these objects evoke an effect that amazes the human mind, which makes him involuntarily proud, admire and takes inspiration to create new works of art. The mass-ideological, educational work of museums, forming an important element of communication, is aimed at forming a mature, socially active person, educating him ideologically, morally, aesthetically, and deepening his knowledge and information. Museums have an impact on different social, professional, and age categories of the population using exposition, video, and many other forms of museum communication. The scope of public work should be considered on the basis of close connection with other directions of museum activity. The ideological-educational, educational work of museums is based on such principles as scientificity and connection with life. Museums are very important in instilling the ideology of national independence in the hearts and minds of our people, in realizing our national identity, in teaching social activity, and in educating a perfect person. The educational potential of museums with a historical profile lies in the use of direct testimonies and original monuments that reflect the multifaceted history of the people based on their specific characteristics. The principle of objectivity not only ensures the originality of the promotion of historical knowledge, but also ensures a high level of evidence, effectiveness and, of course, the activity of "education with history".

Museums, following the modern demands of promotion, strive to convey knowledge in a more reliable, demonstrative and memorable manner as much as possible. a) Museum pedagogy. Modern society is interested in using the ideological, educational and educational opportunities of the museum as efficiently as possible. The need for theoretical and scientific-methodical justification of this line of museum activity determines the emergence of a new special scientific science-museum pedagogy. The subject of museum pedagogy is the content, methods and forms of the pedagogical influence of the museum, the characteristics of the influence of the population on different categories, as well as the problems related to determining the place of the museum in the system of cultural institutions. In this regard, by the museum pedagogy:

- the laws of the museum pedagogical process and their use in practice, the possibilities of increasing the level of pedagogical leadership are studied.

- The characteristics of the museum's pedagogical impact on various social and young groups of the museum audience are determined

- Experiences of ideological-educational, educational activities of museums of different profiles, types, and types are summarized, and scientific methodical instructions are developed and improved on this basis. - More effective forms and methods of cooperation of museums with other educational institutions will be determined.

- The development of the realization of pedagogical possibilities of museums is predicted. Among the issues solved by the museum pedagogy is the activation of various processes of personality formation, such as the development of creative abilities, the development of an active life position. The organization of pedagogical activities in the museum, their management, identification and introduction of new forms is based on the study of the audience's interests and the acquisition of museum information.

Museum pedagogy pays special attention to young people. It is promising to work with children of school age and preschool age. Attracting workers and rural residents to museums

is one of the most urgent problems today. One of the main tasks of museum pedagogy is to train and improve the skills of museum pedagogues and pedagogical content. The scientific and practical achievements of this subject are used in the training of museologists in higher educational institutions, in institutes and courses for improving the qualifications of museum employees, and in the development and implementation of theoretical and practical training programs. The scope of issues developed by museum pedagogy includes the methodology and practice of organizing and planning the organization and development of ideological-educational, educational activities. Types and forms of ideological-educational, educational work of museums. This direction of the museum's activity is considered a part of the pedagogical activity, and new demands are always placed before it, wider opportunities are opened. Its tasks, forms and methods are different.

In our opinion, in the current conditions where New Uzbekistan is being built, the role of national family values is increasing more than ever. In short, national and universal values are a powerful factor for the development of society and its foundation, which conveys the successes achieved in the historical development of the nation from generation to generation. Therefore, let's be a beacon that shows our children the right path so that they can pass through the milestones in the family as they go through childhood, adolescence, and adulthood. In the process of implementing new changes in the society under the conditions of independence, in fulfilling the tasks of educating the members of the society in the spirit of democratic thinking and the national idea, the importance of museums is increasing. Of course, the spirituality of any people or nation cannot be imagined without its history, customs and traditions, life values. Museums and historical architectural monuments in the Republic of Uzbekistan play an important role in the cultural revival of the nation, the promotion of the national idea, the strengthening of national pride and values in the minds of the people, the feeling of loyalty to the ideals of independence, and the strengthening of faith in democracy and development.

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